

- SYNTHESIS OF α/β -ARYL- AND γ -ARYL- γ -BENZYL- γ -BUTYROLACTONES

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Several γ -butyrolactones having methoxy and/or chloro-substituted aryl group on α/β position and aryl and benzyl groups on γ position have been synthesised.

γ -Butyrolactones, synthesised by Rosenmund *et al.* (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, 272, 313; *Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 711) and Nargund *et al.* (*J. Ind. Med. Assoc.*, 1945, 14, 69,73), mainly possessed a substituted aryl group on γ position of the lactone ring. It would be interesting therefore to examine lactones possessing aryl group on α or β position.

α -Aryl- γ -butyrolactones have been synthesised by following the method of Carre and Liebermann (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 196, 117) from substituted benzyl cyanides as shown below :

In this way α -3-chloro-4-methoxy-, 2-methoxy-5-chloro-, 2:4-, 3:4- and 2:5-dichloro-phenyl- γ -butyrolactones were synthesised from the corresponding substituted benzyl cyanides.

β -Aryl- γ -butyrolactones were synthesised from β -arylgutarimides as shown below :

In this way β -3-chloro-4-methoxy-, 2-methoxy-5-chloro-, 2:4-, 3:4- and 2:5-dichloro-phenyl- γ -butyrolactones were prepared from the relatively substituted phenylglutarimides.

Trivedi and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1941, 10, Part 3, 102) prepared $\gamma\gamma$ -disubstituted γ -butyrolactones by the action of alkylmagnesium bromide on ethyl β -aroylpropionates. γ -Benzyl- γ -aryl- γ -butyrolactones have been prepared by the condensation of benzylmagnesium halides with ethyl β -aroylpropionates.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Aryl- γ -butyrolactones.—Substituted benzyl cyanides were prepared from the corresponding aryl aldehydes through benzyl alcohols (Cross-Cannizzaro) and benzyl halides (SOCl₂).

Condensation of Substituted Benzyl Cyanides with Ethylene Chlorhydrin and Preparation of α -Aryl- γ -butyrolactones.—To the sodium salt of substituted benzyl cyanide (from cyanide 0.1 M and sodamide 0.1 M) in dry ether (75 c.c.) was added dry ethylene chlorhydrin (0.1 M) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice and HCl and the resulting hydroxycyanide was heated with NaOH solution (20 g. in 50 c.c. water) for 4 hours. The solution was cooled, after removal of neutral impurities with ether, was washed, acidified with 25% H₂SO₄ and more of this added till its concentration reached 15% (approx.). It was then heated on a water-bath for 2 hours and the semisolid mass was kept over saturated

sodium bicarbonate solution for 24 hours. The insoluble lactone was purified by crystallisation, if solid, or distillation under reduced pressure, if liquid. The overall yield of lactones was 40%.

β-Aryl-γ-butyrolactones.—The required *β*-arylgutarimides were prepared as described by Trivedi *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 677). Monoamide of *β*-arylgutaric acid was dissolved in NaOH (24 g. in 84 c.c. water) solution and to this was added 0.5 *N* sodium hypochlorite (180 c.c.) and the mixture was stirred mechanically for 3 hours. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was exactly neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid when *β*-aryl-*γ*-aminobutyric acid separated. In the case of dihalo-compounds sodium hypobromite was used. To a solution of *β*-aryl-*γ*-aminobutyric acid (0.03 *M*) in 20% H₂SO₄ (40 c.c.) was added an ice-cooled solution of sodium nitrite (2.75 g., 20 c.c.) with vigorous stirring. It was then treated with an equal volume of 20% H₂SO₄ and the solution heated on a water-bath for an hour. The oily product was washed several times with sodium bicarbonate solution and the insoluble lactone was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The yield of the lactone was 50%.

γ-Aryl-γ-benzyl-γ-butyrolactones were prepared by the action of benzylmagnesium chloride and *p*-methoxybenzylmagnesium bromide on ethyl *β*-aroylpropionic acids (Nargund *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1937, **14**, 406; *loc. cit.*) by the method described by Trivedi and Nargund (*loc. cit.*). Compounds prepared are shown in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	M.P. or B.P. & crystal shape.	Formula.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>α</i> -(3-Chloro-4-methoxyphenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 130-35°/0.6 mm.	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	15.8 (230.0)	15.7 226.5)
2.	<i>α</i> -(2-Methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-B	128-29°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	15.4 (228.0)	15.7 226.5)
3.	<i>α</i> -(2:4-Dichlorophenyl)-B	80°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	30.8 (235.0)	30.7 232.0)
4.	<i>α</i> -(3:4-Dichlorophenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 185-89°/1 mm.	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	30.5 (230.0)	30.7 231.0)
5.	<i>α</i> -(2:5-Dichlorophenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 163-68°/1 mm.	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	30.6 (231.0)	30.7 231.0)
6.	<i>β</i> -(3-Chloro-4-methoxyphenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 208-13°/0.5 mm.	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	15.9 (230.0)	15.7 226.5)
7.	<i>β</i> -(2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 158-63°/0.4 mm.	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	15.5 (228.0)	15.7 226.5)
8.	<i>β</i> -(2:4-Dichlorophenyl)-B	70°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	30.9 (234.0)	30.7 231.0)
9.	<i>β</i> -(3:4-Dichlorophenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 185-90°/0.8 mm.	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	30.5 (230.0)	30.7 231.0)
10.	<i>β</i> -(2:5-Dichlorophenyl)-B	Yellow liquid, 170-75°/0.8 mm.	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	30.7 (232.0)	30.7 231.0)
11.	<i>β</i> -(3:4-Dichlorophenyl)- <i>γ</i> -AB	Granules from hot water; 204°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	28.9 (252.0)	28.6 248.0)
12.	<i>β</i> -(2:5-Dichlorophenyl)- <i>γ</i> -AB	Colorless needles from alcohol; 234°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	28.9 (250.0)	28.6 248.0)

B denotes butyrolactone and AB, aminobutyric acid.

* Figures in parenthesis relate to neutral equivalents.

TABLE II

No.	Compounds.	M.P. or B.P. and crystal shape.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	2-Methoxy-5-chlorobenzyl alcohol	Needles from alcohol, 58°	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	Cl: 20.8	20.6
2.	2,5-Dichlorobenzyl cyanide	Do, 83-84°	C ₉ H ₇ NCI ₂	N: 7.7	7.5
3.	Ethyl β-(4-methoxy-3-methylbenzoyl) propionate	Do, 63°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₄	C: 67.0 H: 7.0	67.2 7.2
4.	Ethyl β-(4-chlorobenzoyl)propionate	Do, 56°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	Cl: 15.0	14.8
5.	Monoamide of β-(3-chloro-4-methoxyphenyl)-glutaric acid	Granules from hot water, 147°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ NCI	Cl: 13.3 N.E. 270.0	13.1 271.5
6.	Monoamide of β-(2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-glutaric acid	Colorless needles from hot water, 168°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ NCI	Cl: 13.3 N.E. 274.0	13.1 271.5
7.	Monoamide of β-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-glutaric acid	Do, 199°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ NCI ₂	Cl: 25.9 N.E. 27.5	25.7 276.0
8.	Monoamide of β-(2,5-dichlorophenyl)-glutaric acid	Granules from hot water, 180°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ NCI ₂	Cl: 25.9 N.E. 278.0	25.7 276.0
9.	β-(3-Chloro-4-methoxyphenyl)-γ-aminobutyric acid	Colorless needles from hot water, 132°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCI	Cl: 14.8 N.E. 245.0	14.6 243.5
10.	β-(2-Methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-γ-aminobutyric acid	Do, 175°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCI	Cl: 14.5 N.E. 244.0	14.6 243.5
11.	γ-(Methoxyphenyl) γ-(benzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Do, from dilute alcohol, 87°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₃	C: 76.8 H: 6.6 N.E. 285.0	76.6 6.4 282.0
12.	γ-(4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl)-γ-(benzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Do, 140°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃	C: 77.2 H: 6.9 N.E. 299.0	77.0 6.8 296.0
13.	γ-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-γ-(benzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Do, 137°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C: 73.2 H: 6.6 N.E. 314.0	73.0 6.4 312.0
14.	γ-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-γ-(benzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Yellow liquid, 198-203°/1 mm	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C: 72.2 H: 6.6 N.E. 316.0	73.0 6.4 312.0
15.	γ-(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-γ-(benzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Colorless needles from dilute alcohol, 94°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C: 73.2 H: 6.5 N.E. 315.0	73.0 6.4 312.0
16.	γ-(p-Chlorophenyl)-γ-(benzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Do, 90°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl	Cl: 12.6 N.E. 289.0	12.4 286.5
17.	γ-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-γ-(p-methoxybenzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Yellow liquid, 140-45°/0.3 mm. n _D ²⁰ 1.54°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	C: 73.3 H: 6.6 N.E. 315.0	73.1 6.4 312.0
18.	γ-(4-Methoxy-3-methylphenyl)-γ-(p-methoxybenzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Yellow liquid, 189-93°/1 mm n _D ²⁰ 1.540	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	C: 73.8 H: 6.9 N.E. 328.0	73.6 6.7 326.0
19.	γ-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-γ-(p-methoxybenzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Yellow liquid, 181-85°/0.9 mm n _D ²⁰ 1.543	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅	C: 70.3 H: 6.6 N.E. 346.0	70.2 6.4 342.0
20.	γ-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-γ-(p-methoxybenzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Yellow liquid, 130-35°/0.8 mm n _D ²⁰ 1.529	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅	C: 70.3 H: 6.4 N.E. 346.0	70.2 6.4 342.0
21.	γ-(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-γ-(p-methoxybenzyl)-γ-butyrolactone	Yellow liquid, 183-87°/0.7 mm n _D ²⁰ 1.535	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅	C: 70.1 H: 6.6 N.E. 344.0	70.2 6.4 342.0

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